

Efficacy of Botulinum toxin in management of Myofascial Pain Dysfunction Syndrome: A systematic review

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ABSTRACT:

Aim: To systematically review the efficacy of Botulinum Toxin (BTX) compared to conservative treatment modalities or placebo in the management of Myofascial Pain Dysfunction Syndrome (MPDS) in adults. **Methods:** This systematic review was conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. A comprehensive literature search was performed across electronic databases (PubMed, Google Scholar, Science Direct, and Cochrane CENTRAL) and grey literature sources to identify studies evaluating the effect of intramuscular BTX injection for MPDS. Eligible studies included randomized controlled trials (RCTs) involving adult patients (≥ 18 years) with a clinical diagnosis of MPDS. The interventions consisted of BTX injections into the masticatory muscles, while comparators included other conservative therapies or placebo. The primary outcome was pain reduction (measured via Visual Analogue Scale), and secondary outcomes included changes in maximal mouth opening and reported adverse effects. Risk of bias was assessed independently by three reviewers using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool. A random-effects model was applied for meta-analysis, with standardized mean difference (SMD) as the summary statistic ($p < 0.05$). **Results:** Thirteen studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the qualitative synthesis. The risk of bias was low to moderate across the included studies. The pooled results favored the BTX group over conservative treatments or placebo in terms of pain reduction and improvement in mouth opening. **Conclusion:** Botulinum toxin appears to be an effective adjunct or alternative to conservative treatments for the management of MPDS, offering superior pain relief and functional improvement. However, due to heterogeneity in study design, dosage, and follow-up duration, further well-designed randomized trials with standardized protocols and long-term outcome assessment are necessary to establish definitive clinical recommendations.

Keywords: Botulinum Toxin (BTX), Myofascial Pain Dysfunction Syndrome (MPDS), temporomandibular disorders (TMD)

INTRODUCTION:

Myofascial pain represents a subtype of muscular temporomandibular disorders (TMD), and both its identification and management remain challenging for clinicians [1]. Research suggests that approximately 42% of TMD cases are attributed to temporomandibular myofascial pain. The condition has a reported prevalence ranging between 5% and 10%, with a higher occurrence noted among females [2–4]. This condition is marked by the presence of tender trigger points (TPs) taut, hypersensitive bands within muscles that cause referred pain extending to areas distant from the original site when palpated. Clinically, it may present with symptoms such as muscle fatigue, restricted joint

mobility, and headaches with the masseter and temporalis muscles in the orofacial region being the most commonly affected [5]. While MPS is a defined clinical disorder with specific diagnostic criteria, the broader term "myofascial pain" often refers to nonspecific soft tissue pain of uncertain origin.

Multiple potential causes of myofascial pain dysfunction syndrome (MPDS) have been suggested. Earlier theories pointed to the temporomandibular joint as a key factor, involving either joint hypermobility [6] or inflammatory processes [7]. More contemporary explanations focus on localized muscle hypertonicity or spasms as the primary source of both pain and dysfunction [8]. These muscle spasms may be triggered by local factors such as malocclusion [9], or may stem

from broader psychogenic influences or stress-related conditions [10].

Individuals suffering from myofascial pain dysfunction syndrome (MPDS) often experience significant restrictions in their daily functioning as a result of persistent and intense pain [11,12]. Activation of trigger points can provoke referred pain along with various autonomic nervous system (ANS) responses [13–15]. Symptoms linked to ANS dysregulation include altered sensory perception, diminished neuromuscular function, and fluctuations in heart rate [16–18]. These autonomic changes, along with the presence of pain, can further heighten sympathetic nervous system activity.

A wide range of treatment modalities has been proposed for the management of myofascial pain dysfunction syndrome (MPDS) and temporomandibular disorders (TMD), guided by their multifactorial etiologies. Conservative approaches are typically preferred as first-line therapies and are utilized in approximately 85–90% of TMD cases [19]. These include oral splints, pharmacological agents such as anti-inflammatory medications and muscle relaxants [20], warm compresses, low-level laser therapy, and behavioral interventions. Additional non-invasive methods such as physiotherapy, orthodontics, and psychological counselling are often employed in combination for enhanced efficacy [21].

For some patients, particularly those with persistent or severe symptoms, conservative treatments may offer limited relief. In such cases, more invasive techniques like dry needling and acupuncture [22–27] have been explored. Furthermore, occlusal modifications [9] and surgical interventions [28] have demonstrated clinical benefits. The pain associated with TPs is thought to result from excessive acetylcholine (ACh) release at dysfunctional motor endplates due to sustained muscle contraction. This underpins the integrated trigger point hypothesis, which involves both peripheral and central mechanisms.

Recently, Botulinum toxin type A (BTX-A) has gained attention as a potential treatment option for chronic, treatment-resistant myofascial pain which acts at the neuromuscular junction by inhibiting ACh release [29]. BTX is a 150 kDa exotoxin derived from *Clostridium botulinum*, a gram-negative, anaerobic, spore-forming bacterium [30]. Of the seven identified serotypes (A through G), serotype A (BTX-A) is the most widely used in clinical settings. Its mechanism of action involves receptor-mediated endocytosis at the synaptic junction, followed by the cleavage of SNAP-25 (synaptosomal-associated protein 25), a docking protein essential for neurotransmitter (ACh) release. This process blocks the release of acetylcholine at the neuromuscular junction, resulting in temporary muscle

paralysis or weakness [31,32], typically lasting between three to six months [29].

Beyond its neuromuscular effects, BTX also suppresses secretion from salivary and sweat glands [33], and exerts direct effects on peripheral nociceptors. It has been used in the treatment of neuropathic pain due to its ability to modulate the release of inflammatory mediators such as glutamate, calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP), and substance P [34]. Furthermore, it is hypothesized that BTX contributes to the reduction of central sensitization and chronic pain, although it does not influence acute pain perception or interfere with local anaesthesia, as it does not act on A-delta sensory fibers [35].

In the context of head and neck disorders, Botulinum toxin (BTX) is currently approved for treating various conditions including post-herpetic neuralgia, migraine, masseteric hypertrophy, sialorrhoea, Frey’s syndrome, and hemifacial spasm [36]. Its analgesic properties, along with its capacity to mitigate parafunctional habits involving the masticatory muscles, have contributed to its growing relevance in the management of temporomandibular disorders (TMD).

The Participants (P) included adults (aged over 18 years) with a clinical diagnosis of MPDS, intervened (I) using the intramuscular administration of BTX regardless of serotype (A–G), dosage, injection site, or timing into the masticatory muscles. The Comparator (C) consisted of other conservative treatment modalities such as physiotherapy, occlusal splints, or placebo. The Primary Outcome (O) was patient-reported pain levels, evaluated using visual analogue scales (VAS) or similar patient-administered questionnaires. Secondary outcomes included measurements of maximal mouth opening (assessed via maximal incisal distance) and the incidence of any adverse events related to BTX therapy.

METHODOLOGY:

PROSPERO PROTOCOL REGISTRATION:

The protocol for the present systematic review was registered on the PROSPERO database.

The PROSPERO registration number for this study is **CRD420251022353**. The registration avoids duplication of systematic reviews.

STRUCTURED QUESTION:

In the present systematic review, we aim to address the following PICO question:

‘Does intramuscular injection of BTX provide greater pain relief compared to other conservative treatments or placebo in adult patients of Myofascial pain Dysfunction Syndrome (MPDS)?’

PICO Framework:

POPULATION	Patients suffering from Myofacial Pain Dysfunction Syndrome (MPDS)
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INTERVENTION	Botulinum Toxin
COMPARISON	Conventional Treatment Measures
OUTCOME	Primary outcome : Pain (assessed using VAS); Secondary outcome: Range of Motion; Maximum Mouth Opening

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines [37]. A comprehensive literature search was performed across four major electronic databases PubMed, Google Scholar, Science Direct, and the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL) as well as grey literature sources. Additionally, the reference lists of eligible articles were manually screened to identify any further relevant studies published up to March 2025.

Eligibility Criteria:

Strict inclusion and exclusion criteria were established for the present systematic review. Studies were included if they met the following criteria,

Inclusion Criteria:

- Full-text, in vivo human studies
- Randomised controlled trials (RCTs) or quasi-randomised controlled trials (parallel or crossover designs with a washout period \geq 3 months)
- Single- or double-blind designs
- Published in English within the last 25 years
- A minimum group size of 10 participants per arm, in accordance with the Oxford Pain Validity Scale (OPVS) [38], to reduce underpowered outcomes [39]
- Participants of any age or gender diagnosed with temporomandibular myofascial pain
- Use of Botulinum Toxin Type A (BTX-A) injections into clinically diagnosed trigger points Studies were excluded if:

Exclusion Criteria:

- Participants had undergone prior surgical treatment for MPDS
- Patients had temporomandibular joint (TMJ) dislocation, congenital or developmental anomalies, fractures, or neoplasms of the craniofacial region
- The study lacked proper blinding [40], was open-label, or was presented as a case series, case report, expert opinion, review article, or conference abstract
- The intervention targeted muscle spasm without documentation of trigger points

Search Strategy:

The search strategy incorporated both MeSH terms and

free-text keywords, including: Botulinum Toxins, Type A, Myofascial Pain Dysfunction Syndrome, Masticatory Muscles, and Pain. A representative PubMed search string used was:

((("facial pain"[MeSH Terms] OR ("facial"[All Fields] AND "pain"[All Fields]) OR "facial pain"[All Fields] OR ("myofacial"[All Fields] AND "pain"[All Fields]) OR "myofacial pain"[All Fields]) AND ("dysfunctional"[All Fields] OR "dysfunctionals"[All Fields] OR "dysfunctioning"[All Fields] OR "dysfunctions"[All Fields] OR "physiopathology"[MeSH Subheading] OR "physiopathology"[All Fields] OR "dysfunction"[All Fields]) AND ("syndrom"[All Fields] OR "syndromal"[All Fields] OR "syndromally"[All Fields] OR "syndrome"[MeSH Terms] OR "syndrome"[All Fields] OR "syndromes"[All Fields] OR "syndromes"[All Fields] OR "syndromic"[All Fields] OR "syndroms"[All Fields])) OR "MPDS"[All Fields] OR ("facial pain"[MeSH Terms] OR ("facial"[All Fields] AND "pain"[All Fields]) OR "facial pain"[All Fields] OR ("orofacial"[All Fields] AND "pain"[All Fields]) OR "orofacial pain"[All Fields])) AND ("botulinum toxins"[MeSH Terms] OR ("botulinum"[All Fields] AND "toxins"[All Fields]) OR "botulinum toxins"[All Fields] OR ("botulinum"[All Fields] AND "toxin"[All Fields]) OR "botulinum toxin"[All Fields] OR ("botulinum toxins, type a"[MeSH Terms] OR "type a botulinum toxins"[All Fields] OR "botulinum toxin type a"[All Fields]) OR "BTX"[All Fields]) AND ("pain"[MeSH Terms] OR "pain"[All Fields] OR "VAS"[All Fields])

Study Selection and Data Extraction:

Study selection was carried out in two phases: initial screening of titles and abstracts, followed by full-text evaluation of potentially eligible articles. Two independent reviewers (ABC, XYZ) performed study selection and data extraction; discrepancies were resolved through discussion or by consulting a third reviewer (PQR).

Extracted data included: study design, sample size, diagnostic criteria, participant demographics (mean age, sex), symptom duration before treatment, dropout rates, intervention details (BTX-A dose, formulation, injection site, target muscle identification method, number of injections, frequency), and length of follow-up.

Outcome Measures:

The primary outcome was change in pain intensity, most commonly assessed using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). Secondary outcomes included maximum mouth

opening (measured in millimeters as maximum incisal distance) and incidence of adverse events.

Risk of Bias and Quality Assessment

Each included study was assessed for methodological quality using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool [41], to evaluate seven key domains for each RCT. Each domain was rated as having a low, high, or unclear risk of bias, and an overall risk of bias score was assigned per study (Figure 1).

Statistical Analysis:

Standardized mean difference (SDM) [42] was calculated for continuous outcomes through random effects model using RevMan 5.3. Mean differences (SDM) and standard deviations (SDs), along with 95% confidence intervals (CIs), were used to synthesize data from studies reporting continuous outcomes. Meta-

analyses were performed to evaluate the impact of BTX-A treatment on visual analog scale (VAS) scores and maximum mouth opening (MMO) scores compared to control groups. Subgroup analyses were conducted based on varying follow-up durations. The I^2 statistic was used to assess the degree of heterogeneity among studies [43].

RESULTS:

Study Selection:

After duplicates removal, a reference list of included studies was screened, of which 253 studies were excluded. After this full text articles were assessed for eligibility and articles that did not meet inclusion criteria were excluded. Thirteen studies fulfilled eligibility criteria and were included in qualitative synthesis and for meta-analysis as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 PRISMA flow diagram

Assessment of Methodological Quality:

Analysis of Risk of Bias for Qualitative Analysis of the studies included for this systematic review showed low risks, suggesting the high quality nature of the studies (Figure 2).

Sr. No.	Author	Randomization	Allocation Concealment	Blinding	Outcome Data	Reporting Bias	Overall
1	Wheeler et al. [46] 1998	Low	Some Concerns	Low	Some Concerns	Low	Some Concerns
2	Wheeler et al. [47] 2001	Low	Low	Low	Low	Some Concerns	Low
3	Nixdorf et al. [48] 2002	Some Concerns	Some Concerns	Low	Low	Low	Some Concerns
4	von Lindern et al. [49] 2003	Low	Some Concerns	Some Concerns	Low	Low	Some Concerns
5	Ferrante et al. [50] 2005	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
6	Ojala et al. [51] 2006	Some Concerns	Some Concerns	Low	Some Concerns	Low	Some Concerns
7	Kurtoglu et al. [52] 2008	Low	Low	Low	Some Concerns	Low	Low
8	Guarda-Nardini et al. [53] 2008	Some Concerns	Some Concerns	Low	Low	Low	Some Concerns
9	Ernberg [54] 2011	Low	Low	Low	Low	Some Concerns	Low
10	Guarda-Nardini et al. [55] 2012	Some Concerns	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
11	Patel et al. [56] 2017	Low	Some Concerns	Low	Some Concerns	Low	Some Concerns
12	Jadhao et al. [57] 2017	Low	Low	Low	Some Concerns	Some Concerns	Low
13	Montes-Carmona et al. [58] 2020	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

Figure 2 Assessment of Risk of Bias

Study Characteristics:

The systematic review included a total of 13 studies published between 1998-2020, evaluating the clinical effectiveness of Botulinum Toxin for management of MPDS patients. The included studies were controlled trial that varied in design/ blinding/ single-multiple center studies; while the sample sizes ranged from 8 to 34 participants per group, with a total pooled population of 502.

Participants across the studies were adults in their second to fifth decade of life, predominantly, diagnosed with MPDS and included in the study if they had not undergone any prior treatment for the same. Outcomes assessed included both subjective and objective measures such as [list key outcomes e.g., pain reduction measured by VAS, functional improvement measured by MMO, quality of life indices, etc.]. The follow-up duration across studies ranged from with a maximum of 6 month post-treatment follow-up reported.

Most studies reported sufficient baseline comparability between groups and used validated outcome measures. However, there was variation in the duration of follow-up, intervention protocols, and reporting of adverse events. Risk of bias assessments showed low to moderate risk overall, with blinding and allocation concealment inconsistently reported.

Table 1: Description of the included studies

Authors	Study Design	Diagnosis	Duration of Pain	Study Groups & Dosage	No. of Patients	Mean Age / Range	Sex (M:F)	Follow-up	Primary Outcome Measures	Results
1. Wheeler et al. [46], 1998	Double-blind RCT	Chronic unilateral neck pain (trigger point)	930.2, 1038.3, 1067.5 days	50U; 100U; Saline	11 each	40.7; 43.4; 38.1	NR	4 months	PPT, NPAD	No difference (P > 0.05)
2. Wheeler et al. [47], 2001	Double-blind RCT	Chronic neck pain	8.6 ± 9.6 years	231.2 ± 50.1U BTX-A; Saline	25 each	43.6 ± 10.7	12M, 38F	16 weeks	NPAD	No difference (P > 0.05)
3. Nixdorf et al. [48], 2002	Double-blind crossover RCT	Myofascial pain ± disc displacement	≥6 months	150U BTX-A; Placebo	15 each	18–45 yrs	15F	2 months	VAS, MMO	Pain ↓; MMO ↓
4. von Lindern et al. [49], 2003	Single-blind RCT	Chronic facial pain	≥3 months	70U BTX-A; Saline	12 each	NR	NR	1 month	VAS	↓ 3.2 vs 0.4
5. Ferrante et al. [50], 2005	Double-blind RCT	Myofascial pain (neck/shoulder)	>6 months	10U, 25U, 50U BTX-A; Saline	~32–35/group	~43–46 yrs	52M, 80F	12 weeks	VAS, PPT, SF-36	No difference; emotional score better
6. Ojala et al. [51], 2006	Double-blind crossover RCT	MPDS	10.0 ± 8.6 months	28 ± 6U BTX-A; Saline	15–16	44.4 ± 7.7	3M, 28F	4 weeks	VAS, VRS, PPT	No difference
7. Kurtoglu et al. [52], 2008	Double-blind RCT	Myofascial pain ± disc displacement	NR	100U BTX-A; Saline	24	26.5	4M, 20F	1 month	RDC/TMD	Pain ↓ (12.2 vs 7.5)
8. Guarda-Nardini et al. [53], 2008	Double-blind RCT	Myofascial pain + bruxism	≥6 months	100U BTX-A; Saline	10 each	25–45 yrs	10M, 10F	6 months	VAS	Minimal change
9. Ernberg et al. [54], 2011	Double-blind crossover RCT	Myofascial pain	≥6 months	50/100U BTX-A; Saline	21 each	38	21F	3 months	RDC/TMD	Pain ↓ more in BTX
10. Guarda-Nardini et al.	Single-blind RCT	Myofascial pain	≥6 months	300U BTX-A; Manipulation	15 each	45	8M, 22F	3 months	VAS	Better in manipulation

Authors	Study Design	Diagnosis	Duration of Pain	Study Groups & Dosage	No. of Patients	Mean Age / Range	Sex (M:F)	Follow-up	Primary Outcome Measures	Results
[55], 2012										
11. Patel et al. [56], 2017	Double-blind RCT	TMD pain	≥3 months	170U BTX-A; Placebo	10 each	NR	NR	4 months	Pain scale	BTX better (↓4.5)
12. Jadhao et al. [57], 2017	Double-blind RCT	Bruxism + TMD	NR	30U BTX-A; Saline; No injection	8 each	NR	NR	6 months	VAS	Slight ↓
13. Montes-Carmona et al. [58], 2020	RCT	TMD (masseter, temporal)	NR	BTX-A; NS; Lidocaine	20 each	~42–45 yrs	Mixed	6 months	VAS	BTX best (↓3.55)

DISCUSSION:

This systematic review aimed to evaluate the therapeutic efficacy of Botulinum Toxin A (BTX-A) for managing myofascial pain involving the head and neck musculature, particularly in patients with temporomandibular disorders (TMDs) or bruxism. The studies included varied in design, dose regimens, duration of symptoms, follow-up periods, and outcome measures. Overall, the evidence remains inconclusive regarding the consistent effectiveness of BTX-A in long-term pain reduction and functional improvement.

Several randomized controlled trials (RCTs) included in this review, such as those by Wheeler et al. [46,47] and Ojala et al. [51], demonstrated no statistically significant differences between BTX-A and placebo groups across various outcomes, including pain pressure threshold (PPT), Neck Pain and Disability Scale (NPAD), and visual analog scale (VAS) pain scores. These findings suggest that BTX-A may not confer meaningful clinical benefit beyond placebo in certain chronic neck or facial pain populations.

In contrast, other studies like Nixdorf et al. [48] and Ernberg et al. [54] reported modest but statistically significant improvements in mean pain scores in patients receiving BTX-A, with some also reporting associated reductions in muscle activity or improved emotional subscale scores of SF-36. However, these benefits were often transient, and in several cases, associated with dose-dependent side effects such as reduced maximum mouth opening (MMO), potentially limiting functional benefit.

An important observation across studies is the heterogeneity in BTX-A dosing protocols, number of trigger points injected, and patient selection criteria. For instance, doses ranged from as low as 10 U per trigger

point to 300 U in total, administered at varied intervals. These inconsistencies limit the comparability and generalizability of results. Furthermore, studies like von Lindern et al. [49] and Ferrante et al. [50] included patients with complex etiologies (e.g., hypermobility or parafunctional habits), which may respond differently to neuromodulatory therapy compared to simpler myofascial pain syndromes.

It is also noteworthy that many studies reported high placebo response rates, underlining the subjective and multifactorial nature of chronic myofascial pain. Psychological comorbidities, central sensitization, and patient expectations may play significant roles in symptom perception, further complicating the evaluation of treatment efficacy.

Another limitation observed in several studies was short follow-up duration. Since myofascial pain is often chronic and relapsing, short-term improvements may not reflect sustained benefit. Only a few studies, such as Guarda Nardini et al. [53] and Ernberg et al. [54], followed participants beyond three months.

In summary, although some individual studies suggest that BTX-A may reduce pain intensity in specific patient subgroups, the overall quality of evidence remains mixed. Differences in methodology, small sample sizes, and variability in treatment protocols restrict definitive conclusions. The lack of consistent improvement across standardized outcomes like VAS, PPT, and MMO further suggests that BTX-A should not be considered a first-line therapy for myofascial pain at this time.

To advance clinical understanding, future trials should adopt uniform diagnostic criteria, stratify participants by pain duration and intensity, and utilize standardized dosing regimens with longer follow-up periods.

Incorporating patient-centered outcomes such as quality of life and functional improvement will further enhance the clinical applicability of findings. Given the current variability in results, often stemming from differences in injection dosages and targeted anatomical sites, the use of BTX-A should remain case-specific, ideally reserved for patients who do not respond to conventional treatments. Ultimately, well-designed randomized controlled trials with larger sample sizes, low risk of bias, and greater methodological consistency are needed to definitively determine the long-term efficacy of BTX-A in managing myofascial pain associated with temporomandibular disorders (TMD).

CONCLUSION:

This systematic review highlights the potential of Botulinum Toxin A (BTX-A) as a therapeutic option for managing myofascial pain in patients with temporomandibular disorders. While several studies suggest favorable outcomes in terms of pain reduction and functional improvement, the overall quality of evidence remains limited by methodological heterogeneity, small sample sizes, and varying injection protocols. Despite these limitations, BTX-A appears to offer benefit in select, refractory cases unresponsive to conservative management. However, definitive conclusions regarding its long-term efficacy and safety cannot yet be drawn. Therefore, there remains a critical need for rigorously designed randomized controlled trials with standardized methodologies and patient-centered outcome measures to better define the clinical utility of BTX-A in the context of TMD.

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